

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "A systematic review and meta analysis of social safety nets, women's economic achievements and agency"

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Published on: Sep 16, 2025

URL: <https://unjournal.pubpub.org/pub/evalsumsafetynets>

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ABSTRACT¹

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Social Safety Nets, Women's Economic Achievements and Agency"^[1] ([January 2025 version linked here](#)) which was conditionally accepted at Nature Human Behavior as of April 2025. This meta-analysis examines how social safety nets impact women's economic and empowerment/agency outcomes across 45 LMICs. They broadly find positive impacts on both economic and psychometric outcomes in this domain.² The evaluations mix praise ("rigorous systematic review methodology; sound meta-analysis methods" ... "very timely") and substantive criticism. The intermediate ratings suggest the paper is approximately at the level of work published in a top or marginal 'B-journal'. Both evaluators provide concrete recommendations to improve this paper to make it more credible and useful to policymakers. Masset argues that "average effect sizes shown are not very informative in relation to the policy goal of selecting [the] most effective intervention or the research goal of designing better interventions." He calls for theoretical justification for pooling heterogeneous interventions, separate effect size summaries by intervention type and outcome, and additional explanatory factors in the meta-regression. Sabates-Wheeler requests more practical policy recommendations, as well as greater detail on programme design and context. She notes that "the cost-benefit analysis is limited due to a lack of comprehensive data"; this might be addressed in future work. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Edoardo Masset](#)
2. [Rachel Sabates-Wheeler](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote³)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?⁴ *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Edoardo Masset	60	2.5
Rachel Sabates-Wheeler	77	3.6

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).⁵

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Edoardo Masset

The main strengths of the paper are the use of a rigorous systematic review methodology; the use of sound meta-analysis methods; and the focus on women-level outcomes and on the goal of reducing gender disparities. The results summarise the impact of highly heterogeneous intervention on highly heterogeneous outcomes. The average effect sizes shown are not very informative in relation to the policy goal of selecting most effective intervention or the research goal of designing better interventions. I recommend a) to provide a theoretical justification for pooling highly heterogeneous interventions b) to summarize effect sizes separately by intervention type and outcomes; c) to include further explanatory factors in the meta-regression.

Rachel Sabates-Wheeler

The paper helpfully reviews the impact of social safety nets (SSNs) on gender inequality. It highlights that SSNs can enhance women's economic achievements and agency, particularly through increased labour force participation and decision-making power. However, the effects on care work intensity are not significant. The cost-benefit analysis is limited due to a lack of comprehensive data. The paper is an excellent resource, but needs some improvements on policy suggestions.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1			Evaluator 2	
	Edoardo Masset			Rachel Sabates-Wheeler	
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*
Overall assessment ⁶	60	(50, 70)	Z	77	(71, 80)

Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁸	60	(50, 70)		81	(74, 85)
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁹	40	(30, 50)		72	(68, 77)
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ¹⁰	70	(65, 75)		82	(76, 90)
Logic & communication ¹¹	75	(70, 80)		83	(80, 86)
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹²	75	(65, 85)		91	(85, 94)
Real-world relevance ^{13, 14}	55	(50, 60)		68	(57, 72)
Relevance to global priorities ^{15, 16}	55	(50, 60)		68	(57, 72)

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 Edoardo Masset		Evaluator 2 Rachel Sabates-Wheeler	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	2.5	N/A	3.6	(3.3, 4.5)

What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	2.5	(2, 3)	3.7	(3.4, 3.8)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 			

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ¹⁷	Belief in claim ¹⁸	Suggested robustness checks ¹⁹
Evaluator 1 Edoardo Masset	Social safety net interventions improve women's economic and agency outcomes. Average impact is of 0.11 standard deviations. A secondary claim is that CCT and food voucher and in-kind transfer[s] are much less effective than other social safety net interventions.	Correct to the extent that it calculates an average of effects across a heterogeneous group. Important questions unanswered: Is the impact large? Does it reduce gender disparities? Second statement ... not fully supported by the result presented.	Report results of the meta-analysis per intervention type and per outcome. Consider other metrics (such as percentage changes) to calculate effect sizes. Include 'leadership' and 'aspiration' outcomes. [Meta-regression should control for transfer size, recipient gender, and multicomponent interventions.]

<p>Evaluator 2 Rachel Sabates-Wheeler</p>	<p>The authors [state] that there is sufficient robust quantitative evidence to support the claim that social safety nets (SSNs) have the potential to address gender inequality by enhancing women's economic achievements (specifically labour force participation and productive work intensity) and agency.</p>	<p>I believe this claim fully as within my own work on social protection in lower income countries over the past 20 years, it is clear that SSNs have the ability to support and promote productive and growth impacts.</p>	<p>N/A</p>
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Evaluation manager's discussion

This discussion was written by Sarah A. Reynolds²⁰

Why we chose this study:

This study unites the themes of poverty alleviation and women's empowerment by examining a variety of social safety nets (cash, in-kind, and asset transfers) and their impact on a variety of different types of women's agency outcomes (both economic and psychometric) in 45 low- and middle-income countries. This meta-analysis finds most types of social safety nets increase both female economic achievements and voice. Additionally, the effort of providing a quantified comparison of the impacts along with the theoretical and contextual discussion of why they differ is extremely helpful for interpretation and determining the practicality of implementation for improving the situation of women. This summary of previous research will help to establish a standard for future research to include cost-benefit analysis on areas that have been difficult to measure such as women's agency but are clearly important for individual, household, and community well-being (economic and otherwise).

Summary of the evaluations:

[Edoardo Masset's evaluation](#) provides an excellent analysis of how the paper fits into the current literature and suggestions for directions forward that could improve upon the measurement and comparison of the findings. For example, a separation of the *women's agency* outcomes and the *economic* outcomes may reflect different expected outcome magnitudes in different realms; economic outcomes often have meaningful numeric interpretation that may be lost when standardizing to compare to agency outcomes.

[Rachel Sabates-Wheeler's evaluation](#) focuses on the current policy landscape, emphasizing measurable economic impacts: "The evidence here suggests that SSNs can be seen as an investment given the significant outcomes on economic achievement – especially labour force participation and productive work intensity.

Furthermore, the results show that SSN have strong and positive impacts on voice, autonomy and decision-making." Areas that would be most valuable for future research to further support this conclusion are cost-benefit analysis and a longer-scale to follow-up for agency outcomes.

Paper status, research direction

The version of the paper we evaluated was from January 2025 ([linked here](#)), conditionally accepted at Nature Human Behavior as of April 2025. The work is likely to be published without significant revision at this stage. We expect these evaluations to provide valuable scientific dialogue for moving the research forward and we believe they indicate key areas for future studies to build on this work that will likely become seminal in the field.

References

1. Peterman, Amber, et al. "Social Safety Nets, Women's Economic Achievements and Agency: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis." Center for Global Development Working Papers 684 (2024).

Footnotes

1. This abstract was composed by David Reinstein, incorporating content from the Evaluation Manager's Report and the evaluations themselves. [↵](#)
2. Although Sabates-Wheeler raises particular doubts about the impact on "indicators [of] voice, autonomy, and care work intensity." [↵](#)
3. We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice." [↵](#)
4. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)
5. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
6.
Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.
[↵](#)
7. The methods of analysis are sound, and the results are credible, but they are not very informative. [↵](#)

8. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

9.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

10. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

11. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

12.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↵](#)

13.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↵](#)

14.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

15. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

16.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

17.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. [↵](#)

18. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you *believe* the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. [↵](#)

19.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. ↵

20. David Reinstein made some very small stylistic edits. ↵

References

1. Peterman, Amber, Jingying Wang, Kevin Kamto Sonke, and Janina Steinert. 2024. 'Social Safety Nets, Women's Economic Achievements and Agency: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', March. <https://www.cgdev.org/publication/social-safety-nets-womens-economic-achievements-and-agency-systematic-review-and-meta>. ↵